

Breaking Bias: Measurements, Potentials, and Limitations for Modelling Study Success by Performance and Diversity Factors

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of performance and diversity factors on student success using machine learning models. Two case studies from Austrian universities are presented, comparing the predictive power of models with and without diversity related factors. While performance indicators seem to have larger impact on student success, diversity factors can slightly improve model accuracy and help identify at-risk students. However, the importance of the use of diversity indicators in predictive models varies depending on the study program, the student population and on the aim with which the analysis is carried out. The study highlights the potential and limitations of using machine learning models to predict student success and emphasizes the need for context-specific analysis to avoid generalization and ensure fair and effective interventions.

1. Introduction

Since November 2022, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning have finally arrived in the public consciousness. The release of the large language model GPT-3.5 by OpenAI, which received extensive media coverage, was a key factor in this. In universities and academia, the topic has long been studied and discussed, both publicly and within relevant disciplines. While public discussions often revolve around text-generating or generative AI, this work focuses on analytical AI.

A common theme in the discussions about AI is the criticism that there are often insufficiently reflected biases in the data, which can lead to discrimination. In the context of the prediction of student success, for example, the non-consideration of migration background, social background or educational background could lead to discrimination - or at least to less efficient measures derived from analyses of student success. In general, not taking into account variables having an impact on the target variable, may lead to biased conclusions in both the context of classical statistics and in the application of machine learning models (Kuhn & Johnson, 2013).

Research on AI-based approaches to student success remains limited. While there have been publications in German-speaking countries (Spörk et al., 2021; Schmidt, 2023; Lübcke et al., 2023), these are exceptions. Lübcke et al. (2024) note that research on digital study assistance systems using rule-based AI and machine learning is still manageable. This does not mean that there have been no attempts to use them. However, an exchange of experiences beyond regional boundaries, possible reuse and further development on the basis of existing knowledge is naturally more difficult without sufficient publicity. This gap in research motivates the current study, which presents adaptable models for application across universities. According to experience and studies, predictive, AI-based, models seem to be well suited to use empirical data and results of empirical analyses for student success and teaching development, as it also makes it possible to formulate narratives from quantitative results (Isett & Hicks, 2020) and to involve stakeholders (Wegner et al., 2023; Janson et al., 2024).

Student success can be measured in various ways (cf. e.g. Bornkessel, 2018; Daniel et al., 2019; Falk et al., 2022; Krempkow et al., 2021; Krempkow, 2022; Neugebauer et al., 2021). Objective success criteria such as student success rates, passed exams, grades or credit points and graduates within the standard period of study are often used; sometimes subjective success criteria such as study satisfaction are also used (cf. Petri, 2021).

We prioritize objective success criteria and evaluate student success based examination activity¹. Attempts at steering within the framework of the Performance- Based Funding (PBF) pursued with the new steering model also try to achieve this using such criteria. In PBF models, in addition to student success rates, the study duration or the proportion of graduates within the standard period of study (plus 2 semesters in some cases) are also used (cf. Krempkow, 2020b).

¹ Examination activity is an important criterion for the funding of public universities in the Austrian context. Universities are obliged to reach a pre-defined level of active students, (e.g. students that reach at least 16 ECTS per year) in order not to have to pay any penalties. <https://www.bmbwf.gv.at/Themen/HS-Uni/Hochschulgovernance/Leitthemen/Qualit%C3%A4t-in-der-hochschulischen-Lehre/Pr%C3%BCfungsaktivit%C3%A4t.html>

When considering the factors that contribute to academic success, it is useful to distinguish between institutional and individual factors (Blüthmann et al., 2011; Krempkow, 2020a). Individual factors are usually included in models at universities to explain and predict study success. Individual factors can be divided into entry conditions (e.g. diversity factors such as social background, but also previous school education and knowledge or grades in school), context factors (e.g. employment or caring responsibilities) and factors of the individual study process (e.g. performance factors, learning behaviour and motivation – cf. Heublein et al., 2017; Thiel et al., 2010; Krempkow, 2020a). Although research on the factors influencing academic success varies, all levels significantly impact outcomes. However, performance data (academic or prior school achievements) consistently show the strongest effects in multivariate models.

However, a desired steering effect can only be achieved in principle if at least all the central influencing factors on the target variable to be steered are recorded (cf. e.g. literature reviews in Grande et al., 2013; Krempkow, 2007, 2008). In addition, a change in the central factors must be within the sphere of influence of those responsible at the university. Otherwise, they must be modelled as context factors to be considered, as in performance or quality evaluations, so that corresponding steering attempts can achieve the desired effects (Krempkow, 2015, 2020a).

Empirical analyses in German-speaking universities indicate that student employment significantly affects success (Krempkow, 2020a; Krempkow & Kamm, 2012). Additionally, entry requirements and higher education entrance qualifications, which include diversity factors like age, social, and educational background, also play crucial roles (Thaler, 2021; Krempkow, 2020a; Krempkow, 2020b).

2. Case Studies: Analysis of two Bachelor Programs

The case studies will discuss the influence of performance and diversity indicators on student success, whereas these indicators are measured by a various range of factors (see 2.1.) It demonstrates in which cases complete and incomplete models (e.g., only diversity factors included) can be used in modelling student success.

Our first research question addresses: What is the influence of diversity indicators compared to performance indicators? (RQ 1a). Furthermore and more generally, it is assessed: How good are the machine learning models making use of the chosen predictors and to which extent can we assume that they are complete? (RQ 1b). Second, we assess: How good are predictive models making only use of performance indicators? (RQ 2).

2.1 Sample

Data set 1 includes information on 4,602 students in the 2021/22 academic year, with 50% female students, focusing on performance data such as ECTS credits and learning days spent in the online learning environment, and diversity factors like gender, student origin, social class, and school type, derived from student surveys and administrative records. Data set 2 consists of records from 1,117 students in a Natural Sciences program at another large Austrian public university, with about 59% male students, where males more frequently attended math-focused schools (37% compared to 24% of females). Anonymized data was used to ensure data privacy.

2.2 Methods

We used a variety of Machine-Learning methods to predict student success: A General Linear Model (GLM) with a logistic link function, Random Forests (RF), Boosted Logistic Regression (LogitBoost), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM). For advantages and disadvantages see e.g. Bartok et al. (2024).

In this study, we used ROC curves and AUC to evaluate the performance of the machine learning models for predicting student success. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves are a popular tool in machine learning for evaluating the performance of binary classification models. They plot the true positive rate (TPR) on the y-axis against the false positive rate (FPR) on the x-axis. A good model will have a high TPR and a low FPR, meaning that it will correctly classify most positive cases and few negative cases.

The area under the ROC curve (AUC) is a single measure that summarizes the performance of a model. An AUC of 1 (which means 100% of the area is bottom-right to the ROC), represents a perfect model, while an AUC of 0.5 (which means a triangle of 50% of the area is bottom-right the curve – ROC forms a straight line from (0,0) to (1,1)) representing a model that is no better than guessing.

In addition to ROC curves and AUC, we also used other metrics to evaluate the performance of the models, including accuracy, and Cohen's Kappa. These metrics provide additional insights into the performance of the models and help to ensure that the results are reliable. An introduction to these metrics can be found in Fawcett (2006).

3. Results

The results showed that the GBM had the highest AUC, followed by the RF, LogitBoost, SVM, and GLM. This indicates that GBM was the best performing model in correctly classifying active and non-active students.

RQ 1a: Influence of Diversity and Performance Indicators

Research Question 1a asks: What is the influence of diversity indicators (such as gender, social class, (national) origin, school type, etc.) compared to performance indicators such as diligence (learning activity in an online learning environment) or prior knowledge (ECTS credits from the last semester)?

To answer this question, we first fit a "full" model that includes all aforementioned factors. We then fit a series of reduced models that exclude different sets of factors. We find that the AUC values decrease when diversity factors are excluded, but they decrease even more when performance factors are excluded. This suggests that both diversity and performance factors are important for predicting student success.

Additionally, our analysis reveals that various machine learning models each possess unique advantages and limitations. Random forests have high sensitivity but also high false positive rates. Generalized linear models have lower sensitivity but also lower false positive rates.

RQ 1b: Model Quality of Machine Learning Models

Research Question 1b asks: How good are the predictive models based on machine learning methods? How complete is such a model that includes both performance and diversity factors, as measured by ROC values?

The results show that the performance factors have a much higher variable importance than the diversity factors in both models. This means that the performance indicators are more important for predicting student success in this example.

RQ 2: Model Quality of Models Using Only Performance Indicators

Research Question 2 asks: How good are the predictive models that only use performance indicators?

The results show that the model that excludes diversity factors has similarly high AUC values. This was to be expected, as the predictive quality is only slightly reduced. It is noteworthy that the probability of false positives increases when diversity factors are omitted. This suggests that diversity factors can help to identify students who are at risk of failing.

Quality criteria are initially depicted graphically, followed by tabular representation. The analysis progresses from a comprehensive model to a diversity-factors model, and finally, to a model excluding diversity factors.

3.1 Dataset 1:

In this section, both the performance and the diversity factors are considered in the model. This is followed by a section in which only diversity factors are considered and, in order to have the other point of view, the presentation of results concludes with the models that only consider the performance indicators.

Performance of the “full” models:

As illustrated in Figure 1 the utilization of the learning platform holds the utmost significance in the development of the optimal model (GBM). The other performance indicators also exhibit a substantial impact on the model's creation, whereas personal indicators play a comparatively minor role.

Figure 1 - Full Model Dataset 1 – Performance

Figure 1 shows the values for the AUC in different colors for the different models used in the prediction, which are shown in Table 1. Graduate Boosting Machine (GBM) is the best model which covers 82% of the area under the ROC. The breakpoint in these curves (top left) between 30% and 40% for false positives and between 85% and 95% for false negatives (see also Kappa and Accuracy) indicates whether the different models are models with higher sensitivity or higher specificity. In other subject areas (e.g. in pharmacy or medicine), this may well have higher significance. As the points are hardly different in our case, it makes sense to concentrate exclusively on maximizing the area. This (but also Kappa and Accuracy)

favors the choice of the Graduate Boosting Machine, which is 5% better than the Boosted logistic regression. Compared to the models described below, this is quite a high value.

Table 1 - Model Fit Full Model - Dataset 1

	AUC	Mean Accuracy	Mean Kappa
SVM	0.80	0.80	0.56
GBM	0.82	0.82	0.61
Random Forest	0.79	0.81	0.57
GLM	0.80	0.80	0.57
Boosted logistic regression	0.77	0.79	0.55

Performance of the “diversity factors” models:

Broken down to only diversity factors, it can be shown, that the year of birth has a significant impact on the model's formation. Additionally, whether one or more studies are ongoing concurrently also plays a role. In contrast, the social class, gender, and country of origin of the students have minimal influence.

The performance measurements of these models indicate that their prediction quality is not particularly strong. On the one hand, the suboptimal prognostic quality is undesirable, as it suggests the model does not adequately capture the underlying information. However, this finding can also be interpreted as meaning that the university structures do not systematically disadvantage different groups of students and depend on the homogeneity of the student population at a specific university.

Figure 2 - Diversity Factors Dataset 1 – Performance

Figure 2 shows an area under the curve of 65 % achieved with the random forest model (RF), which represents a very strong reduction in the key figure. Based on diversity factors alone, a prediction of students would not be much better than a random division into active and inactive students.

Table 2 - Model Fit Diversity Factors Model - Dataset 1

	AUC	Mean Accuracy	Mean Kappa
SVM	0.64	0.70	0.29
GBM	0.64	0.70	0.31
Random Forest	0.66	0.68	0.26
GLM	0.64	0.70	0.30
Boosted logistic regression	0.64	0.69	0.30

Performance of the “performance factors” models:

Figure 3 - Performance Factors Dataset 1 – Performance

As anticipated, the Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) model yields the most accurate predictions with this input data, as evidenced by Figure 3. Notably, the similarity in variable weights is evident. However, even in the absence of diversity factors, the model would still exhibit satisfactory performance, with approximately 80% of values correctly predicted, albeit not exactly as effectively as the full model.

This raises the intriguing question of the degree to which these core performance variables may already inherently reflect aspects of student diversity. In other words, to what extent are the diversity factors indirectly manifested within the primary predictive features?

Table 3 - Model Fit Performance Factors Model - Dataset 1

	AUC	Mean Accuracy	Mean Kappa
SVM	0.78	0.78	0.52
GBM	0.80	0.80	0.56
Random Forest	0.77	0.77	0.50
GLM	0.79	0.78	0.52
Boosted logistic regression	0.74	0.78	0.52

3.2 Dataset 2:

Credit points received during the last year are considered as the most important predictor, but also diversity factors such as age, gender and school type seem to play a role.

Performance of the “full” models:

In dataset 2, for the full model, the boosted logistic regression model performs best, resulting in an AUC value of 78%.

Figure 4 - Full Model Dataset 2 – Performance

Table 4 - Model Fit Full Model - Dataset 2

	AUC	Mean Accuracy	Mean Kappa
SVM	0.73	0.83	0.52
GBM	0.75	0.83	0.55
Random Forest	0.71	0.81	0.44
GLM	0.74	0.83	0.53
Boosted logistic regression	0.78	0.81	0.50

Performance of the “diversity factors” models:

Making use of diversity factors only the model fit decreases. Predictions of active and inactive students are no longer better than random guessing (see Table 5)

Figure 5 - Diversity Factors Dataset 2 – Performance

Table 5 - Model Fit Diversity Model - Dataset 2

	AUC	Mean Accuracy	Mean Kappa
SVM	0.50	0.71	0.00
GBM	0.51	0.70	0.01
Random Forest	0.50	0.71	0.00
GLM	0.50	0.70	0.01
Boosted logistic regression	0.50	0.69	0.03

Performance of the “performance factors” models:

If only performance factors are included in the model, the model fit is almost as good as making use of both types of factors, (see Table 4 in comparison to Table 6).

Figure 6 - Performance Factors Dataset 2 – Performance

Table 6 - Model Fit Performance Model - Dataset 2

	AUC	Mean Accuracy	Mean Kappa
SVM	0.73	0.82	0.51
GBM	0.78	0.83	0.54
Random Forest	0.76	0.84	0.53
GLM	0.74	0.82	0.51
Boosted logistic regression	0.77	0.82	0.53

4. Conclusion

Based on the interpretation of the different ROC curves, in both student samples the area under the receiver operating curve is smaller for only diversity related models than for performance related models or complete models. So, in these cases diversity related factors have a smaller measurable impact on student success than performance related factors. Which diversity indicators impact student success, seem to depend on the study program and the diversity of the students in the sample.

It is important to note, that the results of analysis of single student programs cannot be generalized. The comparability of study programs and universities is limited due to different designs, populations, and selection processes. Diversity indicators do not seem to play a major role in the first study program investigated. In the second example of a Natural Sciences Bachelor program age, gender and school type may seem to play an additional role as predictors. Adding these diversity factors does only slightly increase the prediction power of correctly classifying active and inactive students. This aligns with existing literature that performance-based indicators have strong predictive power but does not mean that the usage of diversity based indicators is not relevant for HEIs (Higher Education Institutions), because as it can be seen in the first dataset, it increases the area under the receiver operating curve and therefore the sensitivity and specificity of the model. In addition to predicting student success and dropout, HEIs are also interested in developing study programmes which allow a diverse student body to successfully master their programs. Therefore, investigating the specific effect of these factors, when controlling for performance-based indicators may be of high relevance.

In addition, contextual factors, data availability, and the choice of variables play an important role. In the social sciences, it is difficult to find perfectly uncorrelated variables and to create complete models. Therefore, it is important to interpret one's own results with caution and to consider blind spots. Furthermore, predictive performance and the identified importance of the predictors may vary depending on the operationalisation of student success (Bartok et al., 2021). That is why the study may be repeated with other operationalisations.

Further research is needed to investigate the inner working of the models, e.g. structural equation models (SEM) and hierarchical models. Furthermore, it would be useful to analyse the effects of diversity on student success in different contexts, but also develop a monitoring system of diversity factors to professionally observe these items. Finally, extending the suggested analysis to a variety of different types of study programs may be of relevance in order to generalise the findings presented in this study.

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